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The Digital Grave was created by Dr. Leah Pope Parker (Assistant Professor of English, University of Southern Mississippi) and originally released to the public in March 2020, with an update in August 2023. The online version is available at: <https://dm-sims.herokuapp.com/12>. This PDF approximation of the edition is designed to aid accessibility while the Digital Mappa platform continues to improve. URL links in this PDF should function accurately, but highlighted text indicates links within the DM edition that connect different text files and the glossed manuscript image, but which cannot be replicated in this PDF.

How to Use this Edition

Welcome to the *Digital Grave*!

Where should I begin?

The primary feature of this edition is the glossed and annotated manuscript page from Oxford, Bodleian Library, MS Bodley 343—the page that contains “The Grave.” It is recommended that you start with the **manuscript page**, but if you want to read an edited and/or translated text of the poem first, you can do so.

Reading the manuscript page

This edition provides a unique opportunity to read “The Grave” straight from the manuscript page, even with no previous training in early Middle English or medieval paleography.

Each individual word in the manuscript is underlined in **yellow**. Hovering over or clicking on this **yellow** underline reveals a gloss of:

the transcribed word (“suggested translation”) = OE “Old English headword” (part of speech, parsing details); cf. ME and PDE forms

Note the following abbreviations:

OE: Old English

ME: Middle English

PDE: Present-Day English

In many cases, multiple suggested translations are offered, in order to capture the semantic range and potential ambiguity of the text in early Middle English. This form of ‘polyglossing’

allows readers of the manuscript page to consider for themselves how they want to interpret a word or line. The **yellow** glosses also link to the entry for this word in the Glossary.

Each poetic line in the manuscript is underlined in **green**. Hovering over or clicking on the **green** underline reveals a gloss of the line transcribed, with links to the line in the **Line-by-Line Edition** and the **Modern English Translation**.

Additional glosses on the manuscript page are:

- In **blue**: notes about symbols and scribal notations in this text.
- In **purple**: notes about the state of the manuscript.
- In **orange** and **salmon**: notes about the two scribes who copied “The Grave.”

Each of these glosses link to the relevant entry in the **Manuscript & Textual Notes** page.

In order to read the poem directly from the manuscript page, users can hover over either word-level or line-level glosses to receive guidance for specific words or for complete lines, respectively. To read the manuscript page without glosses or annotations, users can “toggle highlight” by clicking the “eye” symbol in the upper right of the manuscript page viewer.

For example, this is how one might read the first half-line of the poem:

1. First word is “ðe”—hovering over the **yellow** word-level gloss tells me that this is the dative form of OE “ðū” and thus should be translated “for you.”
2. The next word, “wes” uses a “wynn” for the “w,” but the gloss clarifies what that letter is, and confirms that it is an older form of “was.”
3. The third word, “bold,” seems like modern “bold” (as in brave), but the gloss tells me it means a “house” or “dwelling.”
4. Skipping over the erasure—about which the purple link offers more information—the last word of this half-line is “gebyld.” The gloss confirms for me that this is much like what it sounds like: “built.”
5. From the glosses alone, I have: “for you was dwelling built,” but the **green** line-level gloss helps me clean this up by suggesting: “for you a dwelling was built.”

In this way, one might read the entire poem straight from the manuscript page—with just a little help from the glosses.

Other parts of the edition

A full, **semi-diplomatic transcription** of “The Grave” offers typographic approximations of the letter forms and symbols in the manuscript, which may be useful for identifying unclear letters, or for practicing reading the early Middle English without the additional challenge of paleographic reading. For ease of movement within the *Digital Grave* while considering a single

line of the poem, each line of the transcription is highlighted with a “clear” link to the corresponding line **in the manuscript**.

An **edition** of “The Grave” provides a lineated version of the poem, with scribal abbreviations expanded. The edition does not attempt to regularize spelling or emend words, in order to maintain the manuscript’s representation of a transitional phase from late Old English to early Middle English for students of language change. For ease of movement within the *Digital Grave* while considering a single line of the poem, each line of the edition is highlighted with a “clear” link to the corresponding line **on the manuscript page** and in the **translation**.

A **translation** of “The Grave” presents one possible way of translating the poem into Present-Day English. While the goal of polyglossing on the manuscript page itself is to create space for nuance and ambiguity, the offered translation—both in this page of the edition and in the translated line-level glosses—gives an example of how the poem can be adapted into Present-Day English in a consistent and coherent fashion. Much of the richness of the early Middle English, however, is lost, and so each line of the translation is highlighted with a “clear” link to the corresponding line **on the manuscript page**, as well as in the **edition** of “The Grave.”

How to Use the Digital Mappa Interface

Instructions:

- Use a Chrome or Firefox laptop/desktop browser for best results. Touchscreen functionality and mobile browsers may work, but is not fully supported by this version of the platform.
- Click on an item in the sidebar menu to open it. Folders in the sidebar contain sub-collections of items. You can open an item multiple times in the main display if desired.
- Any **colored highlight** (←-rollover for example) you see on an image or text is active and can be rolled over to display a window of annotations and links (to other highlights on texts or images) associated with it.
- To open a link or annotation in one of these rollover windows, first click on the highlight to make the rollover window stay open. Then just click on the link or annotation you want to open.

Other Features:

- You can collapse the sidebar for more viewing space by using clicking on the three-bar icon in the top left corner Click on the same icon to open it again.
- You can change the layout display using the options in the top right of the frame
- You can arrange frames around in the display space by grabbing and dragging title bars.
- There’s a search function available in the top right of the menu bar.

A Note on Accessibility

Engaging with tagged and annotated data in DM 2.0 using a screenreader has been tested on the Chrome browser, using the [ChromeVox Classic Extension](#). Text blocks generally can be read via this screen reader, though some code tags at the beginning or end of text blocks may also be voiced. The DM team is working on securing funding to fully develop accessibility features in future DM releases. In the meantime, the textual components of the *Digital Grave* are available as a readable PDF: <https://www.leahpopeparker.com/digital-grave-pdf>.

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The image of Oxford, Bodleian Library, MS Bodley 343, fol. 170r is provided by the University of Oxford Bodleian Library and used with permission.

Introduction to “The Grave” and Bodley 343

“The Grave” admonishes its second-person audience with reminders that soon they shall die, their body will be buried, and they will endure the lonely decay of the grave. A 25-line poem, copied into an open space in a twelfth-century English manuscript, “The Grave” functions as a *memento mori*: a reminder that you will die. The *memento mori* tradition was ubiquitous in medieval Europe and manifested in poetry, homilies, epitaphs, sculpted tombs, manuscript illustrations, stained glass, wall murals, and beyond. “The Grave” engages motifs from this tradition, such as the format of a dialogue or admonition, the imagination of the grave as a kind of house, and the description of worms that will consume the corpse.

However, “The Grave” is also unique. While it shares some imagery with other texts, no direct source for or text directly influenced by “The Grave” is known to survive. It does share some language and phrasing with “The Soul’s Address to the Body,” a fragmentary soul-and-body poem found in the Worcester Fragments (Moffat 1987). The “Soul’s Address” is the work of the so-called “Tremulous Hand or Worcester,” a scribe with a distinctive tremor and consequent wavering handwriting, who embarked on a program of glossing, translating, and otherwise writing in Old English manuscripts at Worcester during the late twelfth and early thirteenth centuries (Franzen 1991). Because Bodley 343 was also made at or near Worcester in the second half of the twelfth century, it is tempting to see direct influence in some of these shared phrases as Eleanor Heningham (1940) once suggested. However, we should remember that shared language is not definitive proof of direct influence, especially in the world of oral vernacular poetry, where such motifs may appear again and again within an overarching poetic “word hoard.”

“The Grave” is not a “soul-and-body” poem, like that found in the Worcester Fragments, or in the Old English *Soul and Body I* and *II* (in the Vercelli and Exeter Books, respectively), because there is no frame to the second-person address suggesting that the speaker is the soul belonging to the body described in the poem (see Bossy 1976). Similarly, “The Grave” is not a variant on the “dry bones speak” motif (see Cross 1957), because the rotting corpse itself is not speaking. Instead, the soul’s audience is framed as the (living) reader or listener to the poem, being told that *you* will soon die and be buried in your grave. The temporality of the poem makes its addressee even more difficult to pin down. The poem’s “you” appears to be alive in the perpetual present of the poem, but the slipperiness of Old English verb tenses contributes to a sense that the *future* decay of the grave is also happening *now* (see Parker 2022).

“The Grave” survives only in one copy, on **folio 170r of Oxford, Bodleian Library, MS Bodley 343**, which was made in the second half of the twelfth century in the West Midlands of England, possibly at Worcester. The manuscript predominantly contains homilies in Old English, such as those by Ælfric of Eynsham and Wulfstan of York (Irvine 1993). These were thus being copied after the Norman Conquest, but during the period of the linguistic shift from Old to Middle English in which Old English was still being read and copied (Treharne 2012).

In all of Bodley 343, “The Grave” is the only poem, added to an originally blank space in Bodley 343 in a late twelfth- or possibly even early thirteenth-century hand, but the final three lines were added later in a thirteenth-century hand. While the first scribe writes in a clean and even script, the second scribe adds their lines in a cramped and uneven scrawl. Due to its shaky penmanship, the Tremulous Hand of Worcester has even been suggested as a possible identification of this scribe (Ramsay 2002), though Christine Franzen (2010) has compellingly refuted this notion.

Regarding the date of its composition, nothing in the poem indicates that it cannot have been composed prior to the Norman Conquest—like the Ælfrician homily it follows on fol. 170r—but “The Grave” does show substantial shifts from Old into Middle English that suggest it may have been composed in the vernacular contemporaneous to its being written down in Bodley 343, albeit in the style of Old English poetry.

“The Grave” witnesses a transitional moment in the history of the English language: after Old English had lost its prestige and use at the English court following the Norman Conquest of 1066, but before the language maintained by the wider population of England sufficiently differentiated itself from Old English to be definitively called *Middle* English by historical linguists (Kitson 1992, 1997). We might call this stage of the language early Middle English; “The Grave” seems to be positioned between Old English and early Middle English, though it is possible that some of its Old English features result from its author(s) and/or scribe(s) working closely with Old English texts—like those in Bodley 343—or seeking to model their style on Old English verse.

Features of “The Grave” that mark its transitional moment between Old English and early Middle English include:

- Use of the Middle English prefix *i-*, which replaced OE *ge-* for past participles of verbs, e.g., **iboren**, **idiht**, **iloced**, **imeten**, **itinbred**. Notably, though, in the first past participle in the poem, the scribe used the OE form of **gebyld**, despite later in the poem using **ibylde**, the ME form for the same word.
- The retention of vocabulary that moved toward obsolescence during Middle English, e.g., **ac** and **bold**. Old English **wag** (with the meaning of ‘wall’) seems to already have been out of use in Middle English.
- The apparent dropping of OE declension endings, due to prosodic deemphasis and their relative uselessness in communication between speakers of Germanic languages (e.g., between Old English and Old Norse). For example, while the nominative singular use of **molde** in line 2 is formed as expected for a feminine weak noun, the same word appears later as **mold** in the apparent accusative singular (lines 6, 11), which in OE was formulated as *moldean*. Similarly, we see **hōd** (i.e., *hond*, line 12), where we would expect *honde*.

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Using this Edition in the Classroom

Because “The Grave” witnesses a transitional period between Old English and Middle English, it serves as a valuable teaching tool for students both of history of the English language and of English literature more broadly. The following prompts offer examples of how this edition might be used in the classroom in pursuit of particular student learning outcomes.

(NB: These example lessons are phrased as guidelines for instructors, but they may also be given as-is or in slightly modified form directly to students.)

For history of the English language:

Learning outcomes:

- Recognize differences between Old and Middle English.
- Become familiar with the processes by which languages change.
- Practice using editions, glossaries, and dictionaries to learn about language change.

Activity: Language change scavenger hunt. (~45–75 min)

1. Have students in small groups access the *Digital Grave* in class, ideally after being assigned to read the **Introduction** and **Translation** prior to class.
2. Over a limited time period (e.g., 15 min), using any part of the *Digital Grave* and its external links, direct students to identify examples of the following:
 - A verb that appears in both an OE and ME form in “The Grave”;
 - An OE form that would be obsolete by the end of the ME period;
 - Four letter forms that are no longer used in PDE (bonus points for naming what replaced them);
 - An OE/eME word that looks like a PDE word, but is unrelated;
 - An OE/eME word that would have been pronounced fairly similarly to its PDE descendant, but which is spelled quite differently in this period’s orthography;
 - A scribal abbreviation (bonus points for naming a similar abbreviation that we use today);
 - An example of semantic shift from the OE/eME word witnessed in “The Grave” to its PDE descendant;
 - Two (or more) instances of the same letter combination meaning completely unrelated words.
3. When the allotted time has been completed, ask students to compare answers.

For British literature surveys or courses on medieval literature:

Learning outcomes:

- Recognize similarities between early Middle English vocabulary, spelling, and handwriting and those of Present-Day English.

- Appreciate the labor involved in producing handwritten manuscripts and conceptualize medieval scribal practice.
- Practice reading texts in earlier forms of the English language.
- Develop basic paleography skills.

Activity: Reading the poem in its manuscript context. (~75–120 min)

1. Begin with only the **Manuscript** page open (or the manuscript and these instructions).
2. Toggle annotations ‘off’ using the ‘eye’ symbol in the top right corner of the manuscript viewing window.
3. Working individually or in teams, have students attempt to transcribe as much of the manuscript as possible. (Optionally, assign each team a line of the manuscript, so that across the class the whole text is covered.)
4. After the designated amount of time (e.g., 15 min), allow students to open the **Semi-Diplomatic Transcription**, and use it to work on interpreting as much of the text as possible, translating it into Present-Day English.
5. After another designated period of time (e.g., 15 min), allow students to toggle glosses back on for the manuscript page, and use both the glosses and the **Glossary** to develop a translation of their line in the manuscript.
6. As a full class, collect translations of each manuscript line and compare to the **Translation** of “The Grave” provided by this edition.
7. Questions for additional discussion:
 - a. What similarities did you notice between the handwriting in this manuscript and the way we tend to write in English today?
 - b. Once you had a transcription, what aspect of the language was easiest to translate? What was most difficult?
 - c. Why might the scribe have chosen or needed to make erasures?
 - d. Why would a later scribe come back and add to the text in the lower margin?
 - e. What value can we ascribe to this text, given the scribal labor involved in copying it?
 - f. What value does this text have for the study of English literature today?

For courses on history of the book:

Learning outcomes:

- Practice articulating features of scribal hands and identifying differences between them.
- Theorize possible contingencies of scribal practice.

Activity: Could two scribes have been one? (~50–80 min)

1. Invite students to read “The Grave” in **Translation**, either before class or at the start of the activity.
2. Using the **Line-by-line Edition**, show students where on the manuscript page (and in the text) the break between **Scribe 1** and **Scribe 2** falls.

3. Dividing students into groups, give them the challenge of determining whether Scribe 2 could have actually been the same person as Scribe 1, just later in life or in circumstances that otherwise produced variable handwriting. Instruct students to look for the following kinds of evidence across the two parts of the manuscript:
 - Multiple examples of the same letter form, which exhibit either comparable or distinct patterns of penmanship;
 - Similarities (or differences) in spelling; and
 - Indications in the content of the poem (phrasing, word choice, imagery) that suggest whether one scribe or two wrote the two parts of “The Grave.”
4. After a set period of time (e.g. 20–30 minutes), ask each group of students to make a claim regarding whether these two scribes could have actually been the same person. Have students share their evidence and the logic behind their reasoning.
5. Whether or not any groups decide these *are* the same scribe, ask students to consider what might explain such a dramatic change in one scribe’s handwriting.
6. Optional: to wrap up the lesson, have students practice argumentative writing by drafting a thesis and outlining the argument of a 5-page paper that makes the claim either that “The Grave” was copied by only one scribe or that it was copied by two.

Semi-diplomatic Transcription

NB: Letter forms from the manuscript are replicated as closely as possible. Features of the manuscript and paleography are noted in annotations on the manuscript page.

ðe þef bold gebyld. er þu iboren pere. ðe wef molde imynt. er ðu
of moder come. ac hit nef no idiht. ne þeo deopnef imeten. nef gyt
iloked. hu long hit þe were. Nu me þe bringæð. þer ðu beon ſcealt.
Nu me ſceal þe meten. 7 þa mold ſeoðða. Ne bið no þin huf. healice
itinbred. hit bið un heh and lah. þōne þu lift þer inne. ðe helepagef
beoð lage, ſidpages un hege. þe rof bið ibyld. þire brofte ful neh
Swa ðu ſcealt on mold. punien ful cald. Dimme 7 deorcæ: þet den
fulæt on hōd. Dureleaf if þ huf. 7 dearc hit if pið innen. Ðær þu biſt
feſte bi dytt. 7 dæð hefð þa cæge. ladlic if þ eorð huf.

7 grim inne to punien. Ðer þu ſcealt punien. 7 purmeſ þe to deleð. Ðuf ðu
biſt ilegd. 7 ladæft þine fronden. Neft ðu nenne freond. þe þe pyll
faren to. Ðæt efre pule lokien. hu þe þ huf þe likie. Ðæt æfre un don.
ðe wule ða dure. 7 þe æfter lihten. for ſone þu biſt ladlic 7 lad to ifeonne.
For ſone bið þin hæfet. faxes bireued. al bið ðef faxef feirnef forworden. næle hit nan
mit fingref feire ftracien.

The Grave: Edition

- 1 Ðe wes bold gebyld er þu iboren were.
 ðe wes molde imynt er ðu of moder come.
 Ac hit nes no idiht, ne þeo deopnes imeten;
 nes gyt iloced hu long hit þe were.
- 5 Nu me þe bringæð þer ðu beon scealt.
 Nu me sceal þe meten 7 þa mold seoðða.
 Ne bið no þin hus healice itinbred.
 hit bið unheh and lah þonne þu list þer inne.
 ðe helewages beoð lage, sid<e>wages unhege,
- 10 þe rof bið ibyld þire broste ful neh.
 Swa ðu scealt on mold wunien ful cald.
 Dimme 7 deorcæ þet den fulæt on hond.
 Durelas is þæt hus 7 dearc hit is wið innen.
 Ðær þu bist feste bi dytt 7 dæð hefð þa cæge.
- 15 Ladlic is þæt eorð-hus 7 grim inne to wunien.
 Ðer þu scealt wunien 7 wurmes þe todeleð.
 Ðus ðu bist ilegd 7 ladæst þine fronden.
 Nefst ðu nenne freond þe þe wylle faren to.
 Ðæt efre wule lokien hu þe þæt hus þe likie.
- 20 Ðæt æfre undon ðe wule ða dure
 [.....] 7 þe æfter lihten.
 For sone þu bist ladlic 7 lad to iseonne.
 For sone bið þin hæfet faxes bireued,
 al bið ðes faxes feirnes forworden;
- 25 *næle hit nan mit fingres feire stracien.*

The Grave: Translation

- 1 For you a dwelling was built before you were born.
For you dust was determined before you came from a mother.
But it was not arranged, nor the depth measured;
Nor was it yet seen how long it for you should be.
- 5 Now further someone will bring you to where you shall be;
Now further someone will measure you and then the earth.
Nor is your house grandly timbered:
It is unhigh and low when you lie therein;
The covering-walls are low, the side-walls are unhigh,
- 10 The roof is built quite close to your breast.
So you shall dwell in the earth fully cold.
Dim and dark that den shortly turns foul.
Doorless is that house and dark it is within;
There you are firmly confined, and death has the key.
- 15 Loathsome is that earth-house and grim to dwell in.
There you shall abide and worms shall divide you.
Thus you are laid and most loathsome to your friends.
You have no friend who wishes to come to you,
Who will ever look into how that house suit you,
- 20 Who will ever undo that door for you
[.....] and give light to you.
For soon you are loathsome and hateful to see.
For soon your head is bereaved of its hair,
All of your hair's fairness is brought to ruin.
- 25 No one with their fingers gently strokes it.

Manuscript & Textual Notes

Manuscript & Scribes

Oxford, Bodleian Library, MS Bodley 343 is a late twelfth-century manuscript, comprised mostly of Old English homilies written in the late tenth and early eleventh centuries, and likely made at Worcester or nearby in the West Midlands (Ker 1957). The homilies in Bodley 343 are occasionally glossed in the main hand with what Neil Ker describes as “usually EME equivalents of OE words in the text,” though occasionally the EME [early Middle English] is in the text and the gloss provides the OE (1957, p. 368). Evidently there was significant investment during the creation of this manuscript in ‘updating’ Old English texts in order to keep them readable by new generations of readers.

“The Grave” is added to what was previously a blank space on folio 170r by two later scribes, possibly contemporaries, and separated by no more than two generations:

- **Scribe 1** penned the bulk of “The Grave,” lines 1–22. Ker (1957) dates this hand to the late twelfth- or early thirteenth-century, evidently after the completion of the main creation of Bodley 343, since “The Grave” fills a blank space left when a homily was completed in the middle of fol. 170r.
- **Scribe 2** adds the final three lines of “The Grave,” lines 23–25, in a hand that is evidently later than Scribe 1’s, but no later than the first quarter of the thirteenth century (Ramsey 2002). This, however, is difficult to determine with precision because the handwriting is scrawled in the lower margin of the page in irregular and cramped letter forms.

Abbreviations and marks used by these scribes:

- **Punctus**: While punctuation in medieval manuscripts was irregular and did not follow the prescriptive rules of Present-Day English, some familiar punctuation marks did appear. The punctus, which looks like a modern ‘period’ and could appear on the baseline (as the modern period does) or at the middle or top of the line, functioned similarly to the modern period, comma, and semi-colon. In “The Grave,” puncti (plural of punctus) appear to serve all three of these roles, appearing between most lines/half-lines, and are translated into the practice of PDE punctuation in the **Translation**.
- **Tironian et**: The symbol that looks much like an Arabic numeral 7 derives from the Tironian shorthand (developed for use in Latin in the first century BCE) for Latin ‘et,’ which meant ‘and.’ In medieval scribal practice, this symbol commonly replaced vernacular words for ‘and’ as well, such as OE *and* or *ond*. This did not preclude the possibility of actually spelling out *and*, however, as we see in line 8. The Tironian et is still used occasionally in Ireland and Scotland today, while in American English, common abbreviations for ‘and’ include the ampersand (&) and simple plus sign (+).

- **Nasal abbreviation:** A horizontal line over a vowel indicates that a nasal (typically ‘n’ or ‘m’) follows. For example, ‘*hōd*’ abbreviates ‘*hond*’ and ‘*bōne*’ abbreviates ‘*bonne*,’ even though in the latter case one of the two instances of ‘n’ is included anyway.
- **Crossed thorn:** The crossed letter thorn (þ), or ‘þ’ was a scribal abbreviation of Old English *þæt* (‘that’), based on the reproduction of the final letter ‘t’ by crossing the ascender of the ‘þ.’

The portion of folio 170r that contains “The Grave” also bears signs of scribal editing in the form of erasures:

- Following ‘bold’ in line 1, the **first erasure** in “The Grave” is the width of a single letter. It is not clear to the naked eye what was erased.
- The **second erasure** follows ‘hus’ in line 7 and is clearly an (unintended) repetition of the word ‘hus.’
- The **third erasure** follows ‘eorð-hus’ (line 15), and appears to undo the repetition of ‘7 dæð hefð’ (from line 14), probably an instance of scribal ‘eye skip’; that is, the accidental jump between lines when copying an extant text. It appears that the scribe ‘jumped’ from the Tironian et in line 15 back to the Tironian et in line 14 of the poem. Then, the scribe erased too far back into the line, erasing the Tironian et that was still needed in the poem’s line 15. Because for whatever reason, the scribe was not writing back over the erasures (which are distinctly rough and perhaps unsuitable to receive new ink), this would explain why the new Tironian et in line 15 reaches into the left margin as the text is laid out on the manuscript page, and the following word, ‘grim,’ appears to have been originally aligned to be the beginning of the new manuscript line.

Textual Notes

- 1 While **bold** is obsolete in its noun usage, its root survives today through the verb ‘to build’ (attested only in OE as past participle, cf. 1: ‘*gebyld*’ and 10: ‘*ibylde*’), which in turn formed the noun ‘building’ through its participial form.
- 8 **List:** in ME, the verb ‘*liēn*’ took on sexual connotations, and when combined with ME ‘*loue*’ (cf. OE ‘*lah*’ also in line 8) was commonly used metaphorically for defenselessness and vulnerability. See MED.
- 11 There is potentially an internal rhyme here between **bold** and **cald**, presaging ME pronunciation and spelling changes.
- 21 **A half-life is missing here**, though the sense is complete. The missing half-line may have been the first or second half of the line as it stands in this manuscript. The poem consistently uses complete phrases for each poetic line, and so this edition favors the interpretation that the missing material would have formed the first half of a new phrase ending in the extant ‘7 þe æfter lihten.’ The subject could have been the same non-existent friend who will not check on the poem’s audience in the grave, undo the

door, or bring them light. It might have had the sense of something like ‘Who will ever open that earth-house, and thereafter bring light to you.’

- 24 Though **al** (cf. OE *eal*) was sometimes left undeclined even in OE, its form here may participate in the larger shift away from inflectional endings in ME.
- 24 What has generally been transcribed as “forsceden” is not correct—what would have to be an “s” is clearly not the same form as other, more certain, instances of the letter. As Christine Franzen (2010) suggests, this should be read as a letter *wynn*. Likewise, what would need to be an “e” for the “forsceden” reading lacks the extended crossbar that is the distinguishing feature of all such letters “e” in this hand. Rather, the would-be “e” matches quite well the curling of the “r” earlier in this same word and elsewhere in these lines. I agree, therefore, with Franzen’s proposal to take this as “**forworden**,” rather than “forsceden.” The change in meaning is merely local, but not insignificant: from the fairness of one’s hair being shed (*forsceden*) to the fairness of one’s hair perishing or coming to ruin (*forworden*).

Glossary

In this glossary, headwords link to the *Bosworth and Toller Dictionary of Old English Online*. Middle English forms link to the *Middle English Dictionary*, and Present-Day English forms link to the *Oxford English Dictionary*. B&T and MED are both open-access; OED requires library subscription (nb: at this time, hyperlinked PDE words follow the University of Southern Mississippi subscription; for access through your own institution, you may need to enter the Oxford English Dictionary and search for the provided PDE word). Bullet points list attested forms of these words in "The Grave" with links to all instances of that attested form in the manuscript.

ac

OE conjunction; **but; for, because; but yet; but also**

(used in ME in Northern, East Midlands, Southern (except Kentish) dialects until c. 1375 as "ac" - PDE obsolete)

- **ac** (3)

and

OE conjunction; **and**

(ME "[and](#)" - PDE "[and](#)")

- **and** (8)
- 7 = Tironian nota for **and** (6, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 21, 22)

æfre

OE adverb; **ever, always**

(ME "[ever](#)" - PDE "[ever](#)")

- **æfre** (20)
- **efre** (19)

æfter

OE adv.; **after**

(ME "[after](#)" - PDE "[after](#)")

- **æfter** (21)

ǣr

OE adverb; **before, already, some time ago, lately, just now**

(ME "ǣr" - PDE "ere")

- **er** (1, 2)

bedihtan

OE verb; **bedight, furnished, equipped, appointed, disposed, set in order**
(ME “dighten” - PDE “bedight”)

- **bidytt** pres. part. (14)

beōn

OE irregular verb; **to be, exist, become**
(ME “bēn” - PDE “be”)

- **beon** infinitive (5)
- **beoð** 3rd pl. (9)
- **bið** 3rd sg. (7, 8, 10, 23, 24)
- **bist** 2nd sg. (14, 17, 22)

be-reōfan

OE verb; **to bereave, deprive**
(ME “[birēven](#)” - PDE “[bereave](#)”)

- **bireued** past part. (23)

bold

OE noun, neuter; **house, dwelling, building; grave, tomb** (metaphorically)
(ME “bōld”; a house or dwelling, but also a castle or mansion - PDE obsolete)

- **bold** nom. sg. (1)

breōst

OE neut. noun; **breast**
(ME “[brēst](#)” - PDE “[breast](#)”)

- **broste** dat. sg. (10)

bringan

OE verb; **bring, conduct, lead, produce, bear, carry**
(ME “[bringen](#)” -- PDE “[bring](#)”)

- **bringæð** 3rd pl. pres. (5)

byldan

OE verb; **to build**

(ME “[bilden](#)” - PDE “[build](#)”: OED cites “The Grave” as earliest example)

- **gebyld** past part. (1)
- **ibyld** past part. (10)

cæge, -an

OE wk. fem. noun; **key**

(ME "[keie](#)" - PDE "[key](#)")

- **cæge** acc. sg. (14)

cald

OE adjective; **cold**

(ME "[cōld](#)" - PDE "[cold](#)")

- **calde** nom. sg. (11)

cuman

OE verb; **to come, go, happen**

(ME "[cōmen](#)" - PDE "[come](#)")

- **come** 2nd sg. pf. (2)

deāþ

OE masc. noun; **death**

(ME "[dēth](#)" - PDE "[death](#)")

- **dæð** nom. sg. (14)

deorc

OE adjective; **dark, obscure, gloomy, sad**

(ME "[derc, deorc, darc](#)" - PDE "[dark](#)")

- **dearc** neut. nom. sg. (13)
- **deorcæ** neut. nom. sg. (12)

denn

OE neut. noun; **den**

(ME "[den](#)" - PDE "[den](#)")

- **den** nom. sg. (12)

deōpnes

OE noun, fem.; **depth, deepness, abyss**

(ME "[dēpnes\(se\)](#)" - PDE "[deepness](#)": now rare, "depth" is more frequently used)

- **deopnes** fem. nom. sg. (3)

dim

OE adj.; **dim, dark, obscure, hidden**

(ME "[dim](#)" - PDE "[dim](#)")

- **dimme** neut. nom. sg. (12)

dūre

OE noun, fem.; **door**

(ME "[dōr\(e\)](#)" - PDE "[door](#)")

- **dure** acc. sg. (20)

dūreleās

OE adjective; **doorless**

(ME "[durelēas](#)" - PDE "[doorless](#)")

- **dureleas** neut. nom. sg. (13)

eal

OE adj. (sometimes undekl.); **all**

(ME "[al](#)" - PDE "[all](#)")

- **al** (24)

eorþ

OE noun, fem.; **earth**

(ME "[erth\(e\)](#)" - PDE "[earth](#)")

- **eorð** nom. sg. (15)

faran

OE verb; **to go, proceed, travel**

(ME "[fāren](#)" - PDE "[fare](#)")

- **faren** inf. (18)

fægere

OE adverb; **fairly, gently, softly, beautifully**

(ME "[fairli](#)" - PDE "[fairly](#)" [predominantly in other usage])

- **feire** (25)

fægernes

OE fem. noun; **fairness, beauty**

(ME "[fairnes\(se\)](#)" - PDE "[fairness](#)")

- **feirnes** nom. sg. (24)

feax

OE neut. noun; **hair of the head**

(ME "[fax](#)" - PDE [obsolete](#))

- **faxes** gen. sg. (23, 24)

feste

OE adverb; **firmly, fastly**

(ME “fastlī(che)” - PDE “[fastly](#)” [archaic in PDE])

- feste (14)

finger

OE masc. noun; **finger**

(ME “[finger](#)” - PDE “[finger](#)”)

- fingres gen. or dat. pl. (25)

for

OE prep. w/ acc.; **on account of, because of, with, by**

(ME “[for](#)” - PDE “[for](#)”)

- for (22, 23)

forweorþan

OE noun; **to perish, die, become nothing, be undone**

(ME “[forworthen](#)” - PDE “[forworden](#)” [mostly obsolete])

- forworden past part. (24)

freōnd

OE noun; **friend**

(ME “[frēnd](#)” - PDE “[friend](#)”)

- freond acc. sg. (18)
- fronden dat. pl. (17)

ful

OE adverb; **full, perfectly, entirely, very**

(ME “[ful\(l\)](#)” - PDE “[fully](#)”)

- ful (10, 11)

fūlian

OE verb; **rots, decays, becomes foul, putrefies**

(ME “[fōulen](#)” - PDE “[foul](#)” [verb])

- fulæt 3rd sg. (12)

(ge)beran

OE verb; **to birth, give birth; bring forth; bear or carry (as in a womb)**

(ME “[bēren](#)” - PDE “[bear](#)”; its reference to giving birth is now a less common sense)

- iboren past part. (1)

(ge)dihtan

OE verb; **to put in order, disposed, composed, arranged, conspired; ordered, directed, appointed**

(ME “dighen” - PDE “dight”: generally restricted to dialectic use in Scotland and Northern England)

- **idiht** past part. (3)

(ge)lōcian

OE verb; **to see, behold, look at**

(ME “[lōken](#), [lōcen](#)”: substantial dialectic variation in eME and ME - PDE “[look](#)”)

- **iloced** past part. (4)

(ge)metan

OE verb; **to measure**

(ME “[mēten](#)” - PDE “[mete](#),” as in to mete out something)

- **imeten** past participle (3)

(ge)timbran

OE verb; **to make of wood, build, construct**

(ME “[timbren](#)” - PDE “[timber](#)” [archaic])

- **itinbred** past participle (7)

git

Also *giet*: OE adverb; **still, yet**

(ME “[yēt](#),” also numerous other forms including “*zet, yit, yut, yt,*” etc - PDE “[yet](#)”)

- **gyt** (4)

grim

OE adjective; **sharp, bitter, fierce, dire, savage, cruel, grim**

(ME “[grim](#)” - PDE “[grim](#)”)

- **grim** neut. nom. sg. (15)

habban

OE irr. verb; **to have, hold, possess, keep**

(ME “[hāven](#)” - PDE “[have](#)”)

- **hefð** 3rd sg. (14)
- **with negative “ne”**: **Nefst** 2nd sg. (18)

hand

OE fem. noun; **hand, side, power, control**

(ME “hǎnd(e)” - PDE “[hand](#)”)

- **hōd** dat. sg. (12)

heāfod

OE noun; **head, chief, source**

(ME “[hēd](#)” = PDE “[head](#)”)

- **hæfet** nom. sg. (23)

healīce

OE adverb; **highly, excellently**

(ME “heighlī” - PDE “highly”)

- **healice** (7)

hele

OE noun; **covering**

(ME “[hēl\(e\)](#)” - PDE “[hele](#)” [obsolete])

- **hele** (9) + **wages**

hit

OE third-person neuter personal or impersonal pronoun; **it**

(ME “[hit](#),” also “hitte, it, jt, itte” - PDE “[it](#)”)

- **hit** 3rd. neut. nom. sg. (3, 4, 8, 13)
- **hit** 3rd. neut. acc. sg. (25)

hrōf

OE masc. noun; **roof, top, summit**

(ME “[rōf](#)” - PDE “[roof](#)”)

- **rof** nom. sg. (10)

hū

OE adverb; **how**

(ME “[hōu](#)” - PDE “[how](#)”)

- **hu** (4, 19)

hūs

OE neut. noun; **house, family**

(ME “hōus” - PDE “[house](#)”)

- **hus** nom. sg. (7, 13, 15, 19)

inne

OE adverb; **in, within, inside, in-doors**

(ME "[in](#)" - PDE "[in](#)": some crossover with prepositional "[in](#)")

- **inne** (8, 15)
- cf. **wiðinnen** (13)

lang

OE adjective; **long**, of size, space, or duration

(ME "[lōng, lang\(e\)](#)" - PDE "[long](#)")

- **long** neut. nom. sg. (4)

lāð

OE adjective; **causing hate, hateful, loathed, injurious, displeasing**

(ME "[lōth](#)" [rare] - PDE "[loath](#)" [obsolete])

- **lad** nom. sg. (22)
- **ladæst** nom. sg. superlative (17)

laðlic

OE adjective; **loathsome, hateful, detestable, disgusting, horrible**

(ME "[lōthlī](#)" - PDE "[loathly](#)" [archaic form of "loathsome"])

- **ladlic** nom. sg. (15, 22)

licgan

OE verb; **to lie, be at rest, be in bed, lie dead, lie low, fail**

(ME "[līen](#)" - PDE "[lie](#)")

- **list** 2nd sg. pres. (8)
- **ilegd** past part. (17)

līcian

OE verb; **to please**

(ME "[līiken](#)" - PDE "[ylike](#)" [obsolete])

- **likie** 3rd sg. (19)

līhtan

OE verb; **illuminate, bring light (to)**

(ME "[līhten](#)" - PDE "(en)[lighten](#)")

- **lihten** inf. (21)

lōcian

OE verb; **to look, see, gaze, observe, perceive**

(ME "[lōken](#)" - PDE "[look](#)")

- **lokien** inf. (19)

loue

ME adjective from ON; **low**

(PDE "[low](#)")

- **lage** nom. sg. (9)
- **lah** neut. nom. sg. (8)

ma, mæ

OE adverb; **more, moreover, rather, further**

(ME "mǣ" [in part borrowed from French "mais"] - PDE obsolete)

- **me** (5, 6)

metan

OE verb; **measure, mete**

(ME "mēten" - PDE "[mete](#)")

- **meten** infinitive (6)

mid

OE preposition; **with**

(ME "[mid](#)" - PDE [obsolete](#))

- **mit** (25)

mōdor

OE noun; **mother, female parent**

(ME "[mōder](#)" - PDE "[mother](#)")

- **moder** dative (2)

molde

OE noun -an; **mold, dust, dirt, sand; ground, earth; grave (metaphorically)**

(ME "[mōld\(e\)](#)" - PDE "[mould](#)," chiefly in Scotland and parts of England)

- **molde** nom. sg. (2)
- **mold** acc. sg (6, 11)

myntan

OE verb; **to mean, intend, determine**

(ME "[mēnen](#)" - PDE "[mean](#)" as in "intend")

- **imynte** past part. (2)

nā

OE noun, adjective, verb, adverb, prefix; **no, not**

(ME "[nō](#)" - PDE "[no](#)")

- **no** (3, 7)

nān

OE pronoun, combining "ne" + "ān"; **none, not one, no, no one**

(ME "[nōn](#)" - PDE "[none](#)" and "[no one](#)")

- **nan** nom. sg. (25)

nænig

OE adjective, combining "ne" + "ænig"; **not any, none**

(ME merged with "[nōn](#)" - PDE "[none](#)")

- **nenne** masc. acc. sg. (18)

ne

OE conjunction, negative intensifier; **nor, neither, not**

(ME "[ne](#)" - PDE [obsolete](#))

- combined with "[wesan](#)" = "is not"
- combined with "[habban](#)" = "does not have"
- combined with "[willan](#)" = "does not want"
- **ne** (3, 7)

neāh

OE adjective; **near, close, nigh**

(ME "[neigh](#)" - PDE "[nigh](#)")

- **neh** masc. nom. sg. (10)

nū

OE adverb; **now, at the present time**

(ME "[nou](#)" - PDE "[now](#)")

- **nu** (5, 6)

of

OE preposition w/ dative, adverb; **of, from**

(ME "[of](#)" - PDE "[of](#)")

- **of** (2)

on

OE preposition w/ dative/instrumental; **in, on, within, nearby, among**
(ME “on” - PDE “on”)

- **on** (11, 12)

sculan

OE verb; **shall, must, ought, owe**
(ME “shulen” - PDE “shall”)

- **sceal** 3rd sg. (6)
- **scealt** 2nd sg. (5, 11, 16)

se, þæt, sēo

OE demonstrative pronoun; **the, that, those**
(ME “the” - PDE “the”)

- **þeo** fem. nom. sg. (3)
- **þet** neut. nom. sg. (12)
- **þa, ða** fem. acc. sg. (14, 20)
- **þ** = crossed thorn for **þæt** neut. nom. sg. (13, 15, 19)

seōn

OE verb; **to see, perceive with the eyes**
(ME “isēn” - PDE “see”)

- **iseonne** inf. (22)

side

OE fem. noun; **side, flank**
(ME “sīde” - PDE “side”)

- **sid** nom. sg. (9) + **wazes**

siððan

OE adverb; **afterwards, since**
(ME “sitthe” - PDE “sith” [limited in range, archaic])

- **seoðða** (6)

sōna

OE adverb; **soon**
(ME “sōne” - PDE “soon”)

- **sone** (22, 23)

strācian

OE verb; **to stroke**

(ME "[strōken](#)" - PDE "[stroke](#)")

- **stracien** inf. (25)

swa

OE adverb; **so, as, thus, in this way**

(ME "[sō](#)" - PDE "[so](#)")

- **swa** (11)

tō

OE prep. adv.; **to** (denoting literal or figurative motion)

(ME "[tō](#)" - PDE "[to](#)")

- **to** (15, 18, 22)

todælan

OE verb; **to divide, separate, distribute**

(ME "[todelen](#)" - PDE "[deal](#)")

- **todeleō** 3rd pl. (16)

þe, þa, þæt

OE relative pronoun; **who, that, which**

(ME "[that](#)" - PDE "[that](#)")

- **Ðæt** (19, 20)
- **þe** (18)

þā

OE adverb, conjunction; **then, when**

(ME "the" [distinct from "the" as article] - PDE obsolete)

- **þā** (6)

þanne

OE adverb, conjunction; **then, when**

(ME "[þanne](#)" - PDE "[then](#)")

- **þōne** (8)

þær

OE adverb; **where, there**

(ME “[thēr](#)” - PDE “there”: meaning restricted to **there**)

- þer (5, 8)
- ðer (16)
- ðær (14)

ðin

OE adj. and pers.pron.; **your**

(ME “[thīn](#)” - PDE “[thine](#)”)

- þin nom. (7, 23)
- þire gen. (10)
- þine dat. (17)
- ðes nom. pl. (24)

ðū

OE second-person singular personal pronoun; **you**

(eME “[ðou](#)” - ME “[thōu](#)” - PDE “[thou](#)”)

- þu or ðu nominative (1, 2, 5, 8, 11, 14, 16, 17, 18, 22)
- þe accusative (5, 6, 16, 19)
- þin gen.: see entry for ðin, adj. and pers. pron.
- ðe or þe dative (1, 2, 4, 9, 10, 18, 19, 20, 21)

þus

OE adverb; **thus**

(ME “[thus](#)” - PDE “[thus](#)”)

- ðus (17)

undōn

OE verb; **to undo, open**

(ME “[undōn](#)” + PDE “[undo](#)”)

- undon inf. (20)

unheāh

OE adjective; **not high, low**

(ME “[unheigh](#)” - PDE “[unhigh](#)” [uncommon])

- unheh neut. nom. sg. (8)
- unhege fem. nom. sg. (9)

wāg

OE masc. noun; **wall**

(ME obsolete - PDE obsolete [replaced by "wall"])

- **wages** gen. sg. (9 with hele-, 9 with sid-)

weg

OE masc. noun; **way**

(ME "[wei](#)" - PDE "[way](#)")

- **wages** gen. sg. (9 with hele-, 9 with sid-)

wesan

OE irregular verb; **to be** cf. OE "beon" and descendants

(ME forms of "bēn" - PDE forms of "to be," e.g. "was, were")

- **is** 3rd sg. (13, 13, 15)
- **were** 2nd sg. pf. (1)
- **wes** 3rd sg. pf. (1, 2)
- **were** 3rd sg. subj. (4)
- with negative "ne": **nes** 3rd sg. pf. (3, 4)

willan

OE irr. verb; **to wish, want, desire**

(ME "[willen](#)" - PDE "[will](#)")

- **wule** 3rd sg. (indicating future tense) (19, 20)
- **wylle** 3rd sg. (18)
- with negative "ne": **næle** 3rd sg. (25)

wiðinnan

OE adverb; **within**

(ME "[within\(ne\)](#)" - PDE "[within](#)")

- **wiðinnen** (13), cf. **inne**

wunian

OE verb; **dwel, live, remain, abide, endure**

(ME "wōnen" - PDE "[won](#)" [obsolete; archaic in Scottish and Northern English dialects])

- **wunien** inf. (11, 15, 16)

wyrm

OE noun, masc.; **a reptile, serpent, creeping insect, worm**

(ME "[wōrm](#)" - PDE "worm")

- **wurmes** nom. pl. (16)